

EVALUATION OF FIBER MATRIX INTERFACIAL STRENGTH FOR CNT GRAFTED CF/PA6 AT HIGH TEMPERATURE

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Keywords: Carbon nanotubes, Chemical vapor deposition, Fiber/matrix interfacial properties, High temperature, Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics

ABSTRACT

To use Carbon Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastics (CFRTP) as structural materials for automobile, it is necessary to evaluate the mechanical properties under a service environment. Since the mechanical properties of polymer decrease above the glass transition temperature, mechanical properties under a high temperature are required to be improved. The fiber/matrix interfacial properties are reported to be improved by grafting carbon nanotubes (CNTs) on the surface of carbon fibers. However, interfacial properties of CNT-grafted carbon fiber (CNT-CF)/matrix under a high temperature have not been clarified yet. In this study, the influence of high temperature environment on the interfacial properties of CNT-CF/matrix was revealed by single fiber pull-out tests.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastics (CFRTP) have received much attention as structural materials for automotive because of their high specific modulus and high specific strength compared to the conventional metallic materials [1-3]. It is important to evaluate the mechanical properties of CFRTP under service conditions because they are exposed to various environments during actual use. The roof components that have the highest temperature among vehicle structural components rise up to 83.5 °C under the scorching sun. Above the glass transition temperature of polymer, mechanical properties of the composites are affected and reduced [4]. In general the mechanical properties of fiber reinforced plastics are determined not only by the properties of the reinforcing fibers and the matrix, but also by the fiber/matrix interfacial properties [5]. Therefore improvement of the fiber/matrix interfacial properties under high temperatures is expected.

Recently, carbon nanotubes have attracted attention to improve the fiber/matrix interfacial properties [6]. Carbon nanotubes are graphene sheets in the shape of a tube whose diameter is nano-order and have exceptional mechanical, electrical and thermal properties [7-9]. CNTs have been grown by many methods including electric arc discharge, laser ablation, and chemical vapor deposition (CVD) [10-12]. Growth of CNTs on the surface of carbon fibers is a promising approach for improving mechanical, electrical, and thermal properties of a composite. Among various techniques to produce CNTs, CVD is the most promising technology to fabricate CNT grafted carbon fibers. By growing carbon nanotubes on the surface of carbon fibers improvement of fiber/matrix interfacial

properties was reported [13-15]. However, the CNT-CF/matrix interfacial properties under high temperature have not been clarified yet.

In this study, CNTs were grafted onto carbon fiber surfaces by a catalytic chemical vapor deposition method. Single fiber pull-out tests were conducted to evaluate the fiber/matrix interfacial properties at room temperature and 80 °C.

2 MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Material

The carbon fibers used in this study were PAN-based carbon fibers. CNTs were grafted on the surface of carbon fibers by a catalytic chemical vapor deposition method (CCVD). Figure 1 shows a photo of the chemical vapor deposition (CVD) apparatus (MPCVD-70, MICROPHESE CO., LTD., Japan). Ni catalyst was coated onto the carbon fiber surface using electroplating technique. Figure 2 shows the surface of Ni-plated carbon fiber. Ni particle was observed as white dots on the carbon fiber surface. Table 1 shows the condition of CCVD for CNT-grafting to carbon fiber. Ethanol was used as carbon source to grow CNTs on the carbon fiber surface. The morphology of CNTs on the carbon fibers was observed using scanning electron microscope (SEM, JSM-6390LT, JEOL Ltd., Japan) and field-emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM, JSM-7500FD, JEOL Ltd., Japan).

Figure 1: Chemical vapor deposition apparatus.

Figure 2: Surface of Ni-plated carbon fiber.

Temperature (°C)	Holding time (min)	Ethanol (mL/min)	Ar gas (cc/min)
600	30	1	200

Table 1: Condition of CNT-grafting on carbon fibers.

Figure 3: Shape and dimensions of pull out specimen.

Figure 4: Schematic drawing of an embedded fiber.

2.1 Single fiber pull-out test

To evaluate fiber/matrix interfacial shear strength, single fiber pull-out tests were conducted. Figure 3 shows a schematic drawing for preparation of pull-out specimen. Figure 4 shows a schematic drawing of an embedded fiber. Polyamide 6 (PA6, 1013B, Ube Industries, Ltd., Japan) was used for the matrix. After a single fiber was glued to the tab (polyester thin film) with adhesive, it was attached to micromanipulator. After the PA resin was placed on the aluminum plate which was heated at 250 °C, the single fiber was embedded into the resin by operating the micromanipulator. After the designed length of fiber was embedded in the matrix, it was air-cooled. Pull-out tests were performed using a testing machine for micro material (MMT-11 N, Shimadzu Co., Japan, Load capacity: 10 N). After chucking the polyester tab of the pull-out specimen, the supporting part of the tab was cut and the pull-out test was conducted with a constant displacement rate of 1.67×10^{-6} m/s (0.1 mm/min). Pull-out tests were performed at room temperature (R. T.) and 80 °C. Precise embedded fiber length was measured by using SEM after the pull-out tests. The fiber/matrix interfacial shear strength, τ , was calculated as dividing the maximum pulled-out load, F_{max} , by the fiber embedded area, πdl , using the following equation:

$$\tau = \frac{F_{max}}{\pi dl} \quad (1)$$

where d is the fiber diameter and l is the embedded fiber length.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 5 shows SEM observation of the surface morphology of CNT grafted fiber. CNTs are successfully grafted on the surface of carbon fibers at 600 °C by a catalytic chemical vapor deposition method, using ethanol and Ni as a carbon source and a catalyst. Figure 6 shows the relationship between embedded fiber length and maximum load of the load displacement curves for pull-out tests. Figure 7 shows the fiber/matrix interfacial shear strengths of CF/PA6 and CNT-CF/PA6 obtained by the single fiber pull-out tests. The fiber/matrix interfacial shear strength of CNT-CF/PA6 is higher

than that of CF/PA6 regardless of testing temperature. The fiber/matrix interfacial shear strengths for CF/PA6 and CNT-CF/PA6 are decreased by 50 % and 41 % at 80 °C compare to the values at R. T., respectively. The fiber/matrix interfacial shear strengths of CF/PA6 and CNT-CF/PA6 are decreased at 80 °C, but the decreasing ratio of CNT-CF/PA6 is smaller than that of CF/PA6.

Figure 5: SEM observation of CNT-CF.

Figure 6: Relationship between embedded fiber length and maximum load of the load displacement curves (left; pulled-out load, right; fiber fracture load).

Figure 7: Interfacial shear strength.

Figures 8 and 9 show SEM observation of the pulled-out fiber surfaces after the single fiber pull-out tests. For CF/PA6 specimens, the pulled out fiber is relatively smooth regardless of testing temperature (Figure 8(a) and 9(a)), indicating the fracture along the fiber/matrix interface. In the case of CNT-CF/PA6 specimens, the pulled out fiber has relatively rough surface with matrix resin (Figure 8(b) and 9(b)), unlike the smooth neat fibers shown previously. The presence of PA6 residue on the CNT grafted fiber surfaces, points to the enhanced adhesion between the fiber and the matrix. Anchor effect occurred by CNT-grafting is considered to be one reason for the improvement of the interfacial shear strengths.

Figure 8: Pulled-out fiber surface (R. T.).

Figure 8: Pulled-out fiber surface (80°C).

4 CONCLUSIONS

CNTs were grafted on the surface of carbon fibers by a catalytic chemical vapor deposition method, using alcohol as a carbon source. The fiber/matrix interfacial shear strengths of CNT-CF/PA6 are revealed by single fiber pull-out tests at R.T. and 80 °C. The investigation yielded the following conclusions:

1. CNTs were grafted on fiber surface by catalytic chemical vapor deposition method using ethanol as a carbon source and Ni as a catalyst at 600 °C.
2. The fiber/matrix interfacial shear strength of CNT-CF/PA6 is higher than that of CF/PA6 regardless of testing temperature.
3. The fiber/matrix interfacial shear strengths of CF/PA6 and CNT-CF/PA6 were decreased by 50 % and 41 % at 80 °C, respectively. Grafting CNT onto the fiber surface can suppress the degradation of the fiber/matrix interfacial shear strength at 80 °C.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was partially supported by KAKENHI (Japan Society for the Promotion of Science, Grant-in-Aid for Scientific Research (B)) (26289011) and a research project on “Research and Development Center for Advanced Composite Materials” of Doshisha University and MEXT (the Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology, Japan) - Supported Program for the Strategic Research Foundation at Private Universities, 2013-2017, the project S1311036.

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